

THE ROLE OF TOUR OPERATORS AND TRAVEL AGENTS IN THE SALE OF TOURISM PRODUCTS IN NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

Ulker Hasanzade

*teacher of the Department of Municipality and Tourism
Nakhchivan State University*

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7869-1106>

Abstract

The operation mechanism of enterprises in the tourism sector is of great importance. Tourism enterprises build their activities on the basis of different principles. Every business benefits from marketing activities tailored to its structure. Among the businesses that benefit most from tourism marketing activities are travel agencies and tour operators. In modern times, concepts such as investment, natural resources, products or services have lost their meaning, and the focus is on the sale of products and services that anyone can produce and their evaluation or acceptance by consumers.

For this reason, in recent years in the world and in our country, the thoughtful implementation of the obligations of tourism companies and the organization of interesting tours are of great importance. The defined and formed mission of the tourism enterprise is expressed in the form of contacting various advertising companies before starting the activity. Currently, the interests and expectations of consumers come to the fore and are considered the main priorities of their future activities.

Keywords: Tourism, tour operator, travel agent, advertisement, guide.

INTRODUCTION

Nakhchivan, which has a rich cultural and historical heritage and favorable natural conditions, has great development potential in the field of tourism. The promotion of tourism potential in the international world creates ample opportunities for the development of most types of tourism in the autonomous republic.

The main factors that make Nakhchivan an attractive tourist destination are the presence of all the factors that attract tourists, from natural, historical and cultural resources to safety. The unique climatic features of Nakhchivan create conditions for the development of the tourism market in all seasons by using various tourism resources. In addition, more than 20 hotels, many restaurants and cafes, tourism agencies operating in the autonomous republic ensure the development of this region. The hotel industry is an important part of the tourism industry. This increases the importance of colorful and comfortable hotels in the autonomous republic.

Continuous work is being done to develop the tourism potential of the autonomous republic. Various traditions, high modernity and tolerance of the local population in Nakhchivan arouse even greater interest among tourists.

Dozens of advertising and informational materials, videos and films have been prepared about the history, culture, tourist routes, cuisine and traditions of the region.

Nakhchivan is already a place where important business meetings are held, a preferred destination for acquaintance-understanding, treatment-recreation, sports-health and religious-visiting purposes. The development of tourism mainly depends on the presence of professional personnel in this field. In order to provide this region with qualified personnel, special measures are being implemented in the autonomous republic. At present, personnel in the field of tourism are being trained at Nakhchivan State University. Recruitment of personnel to tourism enterprises

operating in this field will be carried out at the expense of local personnel.

Activity mechanism of tour operators and travel agents in Nakhchivan

In modern times, people with limited time organize trips, book a place in transport, book a room in an accommodation facility, deal with visa operations, etc. they need to have some information to perform these operations. The most important service of tourism agencies in this field is that they use their experience and professional level to carry out these operations in accordance with the interests of customers for a certain amount added to the price of the tour. The main reason why individuals buy the services of tourism agencies is to reduce the cost of the tourism product and tour (B. Bilalov, G. Yusupov G. 2012, p. 73).

Tour operators and tourism agencies operating in Nakhchivan operate in the direction of developing the tourism potential of the region and providing tourism services to local and foreign tourists. Nakhchivan attracts attention with its historical, cultural and natural resources, which create great opportunities in the field of tourism.

One of the main tasks facing Nakhchivan tourism is to promote the region on a wider scale. For this, it is important to participate in tourism fairs, organize international tourism campaigns and promote Nakhchivan in foreign countries.

Digital tourism campaigns play an important role in the development of tourism today. Tourism agencies and tour operators operating in Nakhchivan are also trying to attract tourists through online platforms. In this regard, the development of online booking systems and advertising campaigns through social networks is important (Touropoperator 2019).

Cooperation with global tourism platforms is one of the important steps towards the integration of Nakhchivan into international tourism platforms and promotion of tourism services of the region at the

global level. Tour operators can work in this direction and cooperate with platforms providing travel services at the global level (A. Jabbarov, 2015, p. 185).

Although the tourism potential of Nakhchivan has not yet been fully utilized, the research and development plans conducted in this area can further expand the possibilities of attracting tourists to the region in the future. Tour operators and tourism agencies carry out measures aimed at both the development of domestic tourism and the attraction of foreign tourists. Below is detailed information on current developments and prospects in this area:

1. Interregional cooperation: Nakhchivan closely cooperates with other regions of Azerbaijan and neighboring countries, especially with Turkey and Iran in the field of tourism. Within this cooperation, interregional tours are organized by tourism agencies and cross-border tourism is promoted. The air connection between Nakhchivan and Turkey and the land border with Iran contribute to the development of this tourism.

2. Air tourism and air transport: Nakhchivan Airport provides convenient transport services for tourists from other cities of the country and foreign countries. Tour operators offer special tours in this direction, including short-term tour packages, which help attract more tourists to the region.

3. Cultural heritage and festivals: The organization of various cultural events and festivals in Nakhchivan gives tourists an opportunity to get acquainted with the rich cultural heritage of the region. Annual festivals, especially folk art, national dances and musical traditions, are of great interest to tourists. Tour operators offer similar events to tourists within the framework of special tour packages (Jabbarov A. Tourism in the pages of the newspaper "East Gate", 2021 p.149).

4. Capital investments and hotel infrastructure: Construction of new hotels and reconstruction of existing facilities in Nakhchivan has increased investments in this area. This infrastructure development allows tour operators to provide a higher level of service and provides comfortable accommodation for tourists.

5. Alternative types of tourism: In addition to traditional types of tourism in Nakhchivan, alternative tourism destinations are also developing recently. Adventure sports, including mountain biking, paragliding and canoeing, offer tourists new and exciting experiences. This can potentially turn Nakhchivan into a sports tourism center (Kerimova F., Jabbarov A., Isayeva G., Hasanzade U., Bababeyli N., Zeynalov H., Abdullayev A. Development directions of tourism in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, 2022 p. 100).

In order to develop guide services in Nakhchivan, it is necessary to train a new generation of guides. Participation of students in guiding activities is also widespread in foreign countries. But most of them are students of tourism faculty. The revival of tourism activity in the autonomous republic, the organization of tours on existing and proposed additional routes may increase the demand for guide services. Therefore, tour

operators should be interested in training local guides, train them and promote foreign language skills as an important requirement. In this context, the experience of Austria and Switzerland can be used. Therefore, the fact that these countries are mountainous, like Azerbaijan, and that the tourist regions and routes are connected with nature creates similarities in the formation of guides. Guides are trained in technical and professional aspects in well-known tourism training centers of these countries, and trained personnel are trained for 1-2 years. From this point of view, it is possible to train personnel who know foreign languages and study the country's history and geography in Nakhchivan. It would also be appropriate to train guides in secondary education institutions and colleges (Tour operator-tour agent relations 2021).

These tour operators and travel agencies offer a number of services to tourists:

1. Excursion tours are organized: tours are organized to the main historical and cultural monuments of Nakhchivan, including Ashabi-Kahf, Momina Khatun tomb, Duzdag cave and Karabakhlar tomb. These tours are intended for both group and individual tourists (Pashayev N. Travel to the Switzerland of the Caucasus, Nakhchivan. 2022, p. 5).

2. Health tourism services: Nakhchivan is also known for its rich mineral water deposits and healing natural resources. Tourism agencies offer therapeutic tours to Duzdag caves and sanatoriums with mineral waters. These tours are especially popular with people with respiratory conditions.

3. Gastronomic tours: Since the national cuisine of Nakhchivan is rich and colorful, tourism companies also offer special gastronomic tours to introduce local dishes. Tourists have the opportunity to taste and learn the stages of preparation of local dishes such as lavash, kurut and various meat dishes.

4. Mountain tourism and ecotourism: The mountainous areas of Nakhchivan, especially Alinca Castle and Batabat Lake, are ideal places for mountaineering and trekking. Tour operators organize hiking and mountain tours to these regions for adventure and ecotourism enthusiasts.

5. Rural tourism and ethnographic tours: The development of rural tourism and ethnographic tourism in Nakhchivan has been noticeable in recent years. Thanks to these tours, tourists can get acquainted with the life of the Nakhchivan village, local traditions and ancient crafts. These tours are especially interesting because tourists interact with local villagers and observe their daily activities.

CONCLUSION

In order to expand the activities of tour operators and travel agents, it is important to develop infrastructure areas, which are considered the core of the tourism sector in the regions. It is necessary to modernize transport routes and social services, increase the level and variety of services in accommodation facilities. In Azerbaijan, more tourism agencies operate in some tourist centers of the republic. There are tourism agencies in Nakhchivan that promote local tourist facilities and recreation potential, as well as

provide advertising information about existing recreational facilities.

It is necessary to develop the activity of tourism agencies in Nakhchivan. Therefore, it would be appropriate to increase the service level of tourism agencies, to cover more regions, and to expand relations with local and foreign tour operators. In addition to having information about the services of accommodation facilities, it is important for travel agencies to have extensive knowledge of the tourism product being created. It is important that a travel agent has a comprehensive education and knows a certain foreign language. The growing importance of sales and promotional activities, business owner advertising, personal selling, sales development activities, etc. In today's increasingly difficult competition conditions, the importance that tourism enterprises will give to sales and promotion methods in the tourism sector can be taken into account.

Advertising tools play a leading role in almost all countries and cities where tourism is developing and spreading. At the same time, advertising is considered one of the best tools for promoting the domestic tourism market of our country at the international level (J. Mammadov, H. Soltonova, S. Rahimov, 2002, p. 72). By taking advantage of the wide opportunities offered by advertising, we are able to communicate the travel services we offer, as well as the travel products we have, to a wider audience. Studies show that countries where tourism is developing spend 8-10 percent of tourism revenue on advertising. We can say that this figure is only 3-5 percent in our country. Participation in national and international exhibitions is one of the valuable steps taken in the field of tourism development in recent times. However, we see that this strategy alone is not enough to promote the rich tourism potential of our country. I believe that the following factors will attract more tourists:

1. The level of service to local and foreign tourists in our country should be increased, and a balance should be established between the provided services and the price.

2. We should try to increase the range of services. The service is not only accommodation, food, etc. not. We have to welcome tourists with a variety of services.

3. The organization of various interesting trips and activities that will entertain other tourists and stimulate their interest should be considered.

4. Broadcasting of advertisements about our country on foreign television channels is welcomed and contributes to the development of tourism.

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